

Crisis Mapping: Teaching High School ELL Students How To Make Maps That Save Lives

Joel Thomas^{1,*}

¹ University of Miami, Miami, United States; joelthomasteacher@gmail.com

* Author to whom correspondence should be addressed.

This abstract was accepted to the OSMScience 2024 Conference after peer-review.

This conference paper presents the learning experiences and outcomes of a Mini-Mapathon course developed, implemented, and evaluated for the first time in a population of 28 Asian Junior high school English Language Learner (ELL) students in three Human Geography courses at an international high school in Beijing, China. The paper includes an introduction to crisis mapping, an educational website built by the teacher, and a description of the project-based learning Mini-Mapathons. Prior to the high school crisis mapping courses, three Mini-Mapathons were piloted for 75 Asian 4th grade students in three classrooms after they had learned about crises in their IB-PYP curriculum. Kilometers of roads and number of buildings mapped were measured collectively and shared with participants after each Mini-Mapathon. The paper concludes with an analysis of students' knowledge and skill gains, and attitudes towards map making. Other variables measured included students' interest and motivation for participating in future Mapathons or starting YouthMappers chapters in their future colleges or universities. Students' survey responses were analyzed using mixed methods. A recommendation for further research is proposed.

Never has crisis mapping been more relevant, as disasters are increasing in frequency and severity, resulting in billions of dollars in economic loss and a record-breaking number of people being affected [1, 2]. Crisis mapping is defined as "the real-time gathering, visualizing, and analysis of data during conflict and disaster settings" [3]. In response to disasters, a new form of humanitarianism has emerged: digital humanitarianism in the form of crisis mapping [4]. Crisis mapping is an interactive participatory approach revolutionizing the way crises are understood, reported, and managed. A Mini-Mapathon, a 45-60 minute version of a typical three hour Mapathon, is one way to co-create maps so that vulnerable populations, governments, and NGO's can respond to crises as well as increase awareness and preparedness to reduce risks when disaster strikes. The Mini-Mapathon project objectives were three-fold. First, to teach students how to save lives through maps. Second, to provide students a real world educational and volunteering experience that meets their service-learning requirements. Third, to enhance students' Human Geography knowledge and skills. Using the ADDIE (Analyze, Design, Develop, Implement, Evaluate) approach, a Mini-Mapathon curriculum was designed and implemented to answer three research questions below [5].

1. How did the design of Mini-Mapathons support changes in students' perceptions of their crisis mapping knowledge and skills?

Thomas, J. (2025). Crisis Mapping: Teaching High School ELL Students How to Make Maps That Save Lives.

In: Minghini, M., Grinberger, A. Y., & Mooney, P. (Eds.). Proceedings of OSM Science 2024, Nairobi, Kenya, 6-8 September 2024.

Available at <https://zenodo.org/communities/osmscience-2024>. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17352871](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17352871)

2. How did the participation in the Mini-Mapathon support students' expression of interest in crisis mapping in the future?

3. How did the Mini-Mapathon support students in engaging crisis mapping?

Twenty-eight Asian high school students participated in the Mini-Mapathon so that medicine and services could be delivered to vulnerable populations in Nigeria and Zimbabwe by *Doctors Without Borders* and *The Red Cross*. The Mini-Mapathons for ELL elementary students and ELL high school students were inspired by the Mini-Mapathons launched effectively with 10 year old students in Milan, Italy [6]. After www.hotosm.org accounts were created and students embarked on a virtual field trip to meet the vulnerable population in their geographic area via 2-3 minute YouTube videos from *UNHCR*, *Red Cross*, or *Doctors Without Borders*, step by step in class instructions were implemented to make learning visible and meet the academic language needs of the ELL students [7,8]. During the 45-minute Mini-Mapathons, students were taught how to map buildings and roads using software on www.hotosm.org. Pre and post surveys were collected so that researchers could better understand and measure how students learned during Mini-Mapathons and determine if this innovative methodology for teaching crisis mapping was effective [5].

Figure 1. Photos from the Mini-Mapathon with ELL students for Chad, Africa

In response to *RQ 1 How did the design support changes in students' perceptions of increasing their crisis mapping knowledge and skills?* findings indicated that ELL students effectively increased their geospatial knowledge and skills following their experiential learning of map-making because they were able to follow instructions and construct a crisis map [9]. The process of students learning was through the concrete, transformational experience of creating a map that could be used in the real world [9]. Students' self-assessment of their skills also indicated improvement after the Mini-Mapathon intervention with *Pre Survey Q.3. How would you rate digital map making skills?* mean value 2.92 compared to a mean value of 3.27 in *Post Survey Q.5. How would you rate your digital map making skills?* Many students reported they learned that maps could be collaboratively created by many people and international relief organizations need our help showcasing the tenets of *Connectivism Theory* at work [10]. Finally, through this innovative learning experience, participants were able to gain service-learning hours to meet their requirement to graduate high school through this project-based learning (PBL) Mini-Mapathon.

In response to *Post Survey Q.3 What didn't you know before?*, when given multiple choice along with an open ended answer, 43% of the students indicated they didn't know that maps can be made by many people, 32% learned that maps can be created, and 21% learned

that humanitarian organizations need our help making maps that can be used by their organization. 4% indicated they didn't know mapping is never finished work.

In response to *RQ 2 How did participating in the Mini-Mapathon support student expressed interest in crisis mapping in the future?* Most students indicated they would like to participate in crisis mapping again in the future. Based on survey results of Post Survey Q.7 *What is the likelihood that you would participate in another Mapathon in the future?*, 50% of students said they would be interested in participating in a Mapathon again in high school or university which suggests a positive trend in students' map making experience. Students were also asked if they wanted to lead a crisis mapping chapter in the future. Based on survey results of Post Survey Q.8. *What is the likelihood that you would participate or start a Youth Mappers club at your college or university in the future* two-fifths (43%) stated they would likely or very likely participate in or start a *Youth Mappers* club at their college or university in the future.

In response to RQ 3 How did the Mini-Mapathon support students in engaging crisis mapping? findings indicated that 54% of students indicated that this was the first time constructing a map according to survey results of *Pre Survey Q.6 Have you ever created a map before?* From a constructionist perspective, given that this was fifteen students' first experience map making, we can say that this hands-on, computer-based student learning experience was engaging enough for them to learn because they co-created a tangible product or map [11]. Evidence for learning was that students demonstrated their knowledge to create the map and the number of buildings and kilometers of roads mapped collectively were counted at the end of each class [9].

Student learning through this applied research project follows the literature describing students' positive learning outcomes from a responsive curriculum on disasters [12]. The Mini-Mapathon provided an academic opportunity to critically reflect on current, relevant, and timely disasters affecting vulnerable populations and learn from others' experiences through videos, maps, and text from project descriptions [13]. In this way it met many of the "Optimal Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) Curriculum Practices" including but not limited to, students being given opportunities to assume a catalytic role within local community disaster risk reduction and students being given opportunities to practice disaster risk reduction skills in real life context through action learning [14].

There were several limitations and constraints that impacted sample size and how this project was implemented. First, time was a major limiting factor which led to the shrinking of a 3 hour Mapathon into three 45 minute Mini-Mapathons held in each of the Human Geography classes. Language was also a constraint as some ELL students had very high English language proficiency while others had low English level proficiency. Some students were unable to use the <https://tasks.hotosm.org> mapping software on certain browsers on their tablet devices. Finally, many students were absent due to COVID-19, which resulted in a smaller sample size. Given these similar constraints and limitations in the future, two recommendations for Mini-Mapathons for ELL students would be to move the mapping event into the school's library with 30 desktop Macs and ensure users were already logged into <https://tasks.hotosm.org> using anonymous student ID's in order to save time and reduce IT-related issues with students' tablet devices. Another culturally sensitive recommendation would be to implement Mini-Mapathons in the fall semester in Chinese high schools, as there are often more absences in the spring semester for junior high school students who are granted leave to focus on college applications.

In closing, crisis mapping teaches students that they can change the world one map at a time. Through this innovative, experiential learning activity which many students called “outstanding”, students learned that they can meet service-learning requirements in high school or university through crisis mapping [9]. Crisis mapping can also provide students access to scholarships, internships, and leadership opportunities to create or join a *Maptivist* chapter in high school or *YouthMappers* chapter in their future university. Findings from this Mini-Mapathon project suggested that despite English being a second language for the students, the curriculum and instructions in English were intuitive and engaging enough for students to construct the maps in context, even for first-time mappers [11]. Overall, through participating in this crisis mapping activity students demonstrated improved mapping skills, increased geospatial knowledge, and many indicated they would be interested in participating in crisis mapping events in the future. An innovative instructional website was created, www.crisismapping.weebly.com to supplement <https://teachosm.org> materials for teachers to use as an instructional resource when hosting their very own Mini-Mapathon or to provide crisis mapping instruction to their grade 4-university students to use in formal and informal learning environments around the world.

References

- [1] CRED and UNDRR (2019). The human cost of disasters: An overview of the last 20 years 2000-2019. Retrieved from <https://www.undrr.org/media/48008/download>
- [2] NOAA (2021). Billion-Dollar Weather and Climate Disasters. Retrieved from <https://www.ncdc.noaa.gov/billions>
- [3] Mangones, A. (2022). Mapping and Geospatial Data. Retrieved from <https://preparecenter.org/topic/mapping-and-geospatial-data>
- [4] Meier, P. (2015). *Digital humanitarians: how big data is changing the face of humanitarian response*. Crc Press.
- [5] Branch, R. M. (2009). *Instructional Design: The ADDIE Approach*. Springer, New York.
- [6] Gaspari, F., Stucchi, L., Bratic, G., Jovanovic, D., Ponti, C., Biagi, L. G. A., & Brovelli, M. A. (2021). Innovation In Teaching: The Polimappers Collaborative and Humanitarian Mapping Course At Politecnico di Milano. *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*, XLVI-4/W2-2021, 63–69.
- [7] Hattie, J. (2008). *Visible learning: A synthesis of over 800 meta-analyses relating to achievement*. Routledge, London.
- [8] Yoder, P. J., Kibler, A., & van Hover, S. (2016). Instruction for English language learners in the social studies classroom: A meta-synthesis. *Social studies research and practice*, 11(1), 20–39.
- [9] Kolb, D. A. (1984). *Experiential learning: experience as the source of learning and development*. Prentice Hall, NJ.
- [10] Siemens, G. (2005). Connectivism: A learning theory for the digital age. *International Journal of Instructional Technology and Distance Learning*, 2(1).
- [11] Papert, S. (1986). Constructionism: A new opportunity for elementary science education. Retrieved from <https://dailypapert.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/Constructionism-NSF-Proposal.pdf>
- [12] O'Steen, B., & Perry, L. (2012). Service-learning as a responsive and engaging curriculum: A higher education institution's response to natural disaster. *Curriculum Matters*, 8, 171–183.
- [13] Johnson, V. A., Ronan, K. R., Johnston, D. M., & Peace, R. (2014). Evaluations of disaster education programs for children: A methodological review. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 9, 107–123.
- [14] Selby, D., & Kagawa, F. (2012). Disaster risk reduction in school curricula: case studies from thirty countries. Retrieved from <https://tinyurl.com/4nds8998>